

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP4 – Establishment of a non-commercial, Europe-wide breast milk biobank and analytical centre

D4.9: Report with publications on the results of the demonstration studies & cross validation with WP3 plus recommendations

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V4.9.1	03-12-2024	Draft sent to WP 4 team
V4.9.2	06-12-2024	Final version sent to PMO

Abstract

In the Framework of ConcePTION six human lactation demonstration studies have been carried out, investigating the effects of medicines (amoxicillin, levocetirizine, metformin, prednisolone, setraline and venlafaxine) taken during breastfeeding to help women make informed decisions about taking medicines during breastfeeding. The investigator driven demonstration studies performed within ConcePTION have been set up according to standardised protocols. All protocols have been approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities and registered at EU-PAS displayed in the HMA-EMA Catalogues, EudraCT and followed ICH-GCP requirements.

Analyses and publications are published or ongoing for levocetirizine, amoxicilline and setraline. For venlafaxine only two women could be recruited, for metformin and prednisolone sampling is ongoing and will continue throughout 2025, in accordance with the approved clinical trial protocols. The results of these demonstration studies in terms of analytical conclusions, including comparison with results from *in vitro* studies in WP 3, will therefore not be ready until the end of 2025.

Methods

Methods for pharmacokinetic analyses are presented in D4.6 and D4.7.

Results

Levocetirizine

Runned by University of Oslo with PI: Hedvig Marie Egeland Nordeng. A milk only study with sampling at 32 participating breastfeeding women's homes. Ethical approval was obtained June 2021. Recruitment started July 2021 with the first patient enrolled mid-July 2021. Recruitment of 32 patients was completed by December 2021. Bioanalytical analyses were completed in 2022, manuscript submitted in 2023 and published in 2024.

A population-based pharmacokinetic (PopPK) model using NONlinear Mixed Effects Modeling (NONMEM) was developed to predict cetirizine levels in breast milk. The PopPK model found a low mean relative infant dose (RID) of less than 2%, with a maximum RID of less than 4% at peak concentration. Moreover, the PopPK model identified that breast milk pumping time influenced predicted cetirizine breast milk concentration levels, while other maternal and infant factors had minimal impact.

Results

(levo)cetirizine levels in breast milk are low and compatible with breastfeeding. A fully breastfed infant would receive approximately 2.5 µg/kg/day of cetirizine and 1.1 µg/kg/day of levocetirizine through breast milk—about 1/100 to 1/200 of a therapeutic dose for a 10 kg infant.

Publications

Nordeng H, Wegler C, Lindqvist A, Melander E, Magnusson M, Gandia P, Panchaud A, Baranczewski P, Spigset O. Transfer of cetirizine/levocetirizine into human breast milk and estimation of drug exposure to infants through breastfeeding: A human lactation study from the ConcePTION project. *Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol.* 2024 Jan;134(1):153-164. doi: 10.1111/bcpt.13948. Epub 2023 Nov 13. PMID: 37811726.

Melander E, Nielsen EI, Lindqvist A, Hovd M, Gandia P, Panchaud A, Guidi M, Annaert P, Baranczewski P, Spigset O, Nordeng H. Population pharmacokinetic modelling of cetirizine concentrations in human breast

milk-A contribution from the ConcePTION project. Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol. 2024 Nov 4. doi: 10.1111/bcpt.14100. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 39497323.

Significance

The study demonstrates how human lactation studies and modelling approaches may inform product labels and improve clinical guidelines, providing clarity for healthcare providers and breastfeeding mothers. Home-sampling and recruitment via social media worked efficiently to recruit the target study sample in approximately 6 months.

Venlafaxine

Runned by CHUV, centre hospitalier universitaire vaudois in Lausanne with PI: Alice Panchaud.

A milk only study with sampling at 2 participating breastfeeding women's homes. Modelling and analyses ongoing.

Setraline – Proof of concept

Runned by CHUV, centre hospitalier universitaire vaudois in Lausanne with PI: Alice Panchaud.

Thirty-eight women treated with sertraline were included in the study and provided 89 maternal plasma, 29 cord blood and 107 breast milk samples. Sertraline clearance was reduced by 42% in CYP2C19 poor metabolizers compared to other phenotypes. Doubling milk fat content increased the MPR by 95%. Simulations suggested a median daily infant dosage of $6.9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ after a 50 mg maternal daily dose, representing 0.95% of the weight-adjusted maternal dose. Median cord blood concentrations could range from 3.29 to 33.23 ng mL^{-1} after maternal daily doses between 25 and 150 mg. -> Infant exposure to sertraline, influenced by CYP2C19 phenotype.

Amoxicilline

Runned by Toulouse University Hospital with PI: Peggy Gandia

A milk and mothers plasma study with 25 women participating, providing a total of 75 maternal plasma and 75 breast milk samples.

Results

No adverse effects on the newborns were reported throughout the study. The variability in amoxicillin absorption, plasma clearance, and plasma volume could not be attributed to socio-demographic factors (such as the mother's age and weight, or the newborn's age, weight and sex) or clinical covariates (including the mother's medical history, kidney function and co-prescriptions). The median milk-to-plasma ratio was approximately 9% and the mean relative infant dose (RID) of 0.1%.

Significance

These preliminary results offer reassurance regarding the safety of amoxicillin use during breastfeeding.

Metformin

Runned by Uppsala University in collaboration with Department of obstetrics, Sahlgrenska hospital, Östra, Göteborg and Department of obstetrics and Gynecology, Örebro Universitetssjukhus, Örebro University Hospital, with PI: Mats Hansson

A milk, mother's and infant's plasma study. Sampling is ongoing, as of today 14 (out of 30) women and infants have been recruited. Clinical trial planned to continue in 2025.

Publication manuscript of clinical trial and the context of type 2 diabetes, *Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfed children - a contribution to the risk/benefit balance in treatment of type 2 diabetes*, in preparation.

Prednisolone

Runned by Uppsala University in collaboration with Astrid Lindgren Children's Hospital in Stockholm, Södra Älvsborgs Hospital in Borås and Umeå University Hospital, with PI: Mats Hansson.

A milk, mother's and infant's plasma study. Sampling is ongoing, as of today 10 (out of 30) women and infants have been recruited. Clinical trial planned to continue in 2025.

Publication manuscript of clinical trial submitted to BMJ-Open, *Transfer of prednisolone into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - a Swedish low-intervention clinical trial*.

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Discussion

The milk-only levocetizerine demonstration study was based on homesampling. Recruitment via social media was an efficient way to recruit donors, and in 6 months the target sample number of women using levoctrizine was reached. Efficient recruitment was likely due to recruitment across the entire country and levocetizerine being a relatively common medication.

Demonstration studies involving clinical partners (amoxicilline, metformin and prednisolone) have been delayed to difficulties in engaging clinical partners for research while they were busy with post-pandemic clinical duties. Amoxicilline has now been completed and results are coming. Metformin and prednisolone studies will continue until planned number of participants (30 women and 30 infants for each compound) have been recruited.

Conclusion

These results so far offer reassurance regarding the safety of drugs use for some of these drugs during breastfeeding, but data for metformin and prednisolone are not ready yet.